

closed. The percentage of infested stems and the average number of nematodes per stem (P) were estimated using the procedure described by Cox and Rahman (IRRN 4 [3]:10–11).

In early July, a field with plants showing symptoms of ufra attack (a faint chlorotic splash pattern on the young leaves), sown in early March, was found

at Matlab Bazar in south Comilla.

Samples were taken from this field on alternate weeks (see figure).

The percentage of infested stems first decreased as the water level rose from less than 0.3 m to more than 2.5 m. Some heavily infested stems were submerged, providing a source of nematodes for secondary infestation by waterborne

inoculum. After that, the growth of the percentage of infestation was similar in the tank and in the field. The 3-week lag between the 2 growth curves represents the difference in time of flooding. The growth in average number of nematodes per stem also corresponded closely. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Rice root weevil in Haryana

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The rice root weevil, formerly a minor pest, has destroyed rice crops in Haryana in the past 3–4 years.

The attack is mainly by *Hydronomolus molitor* Faust (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). Another allied species, *Bagous* sp., occurs with it. Its infestation of rice in India may be the first so far recorded. The grubs of the two species are similar in appearance, but the adults can easily be distinguished. *H. molitor* adults are shorter than *Bagous* adults (4.0–4.5 cm vs 4.5–5.0 cm long), and thicker.

These species and the white grub *Holotrichia insularis* Br. are comparable in nature of damage and life cycle. The grubs feed on rice roots from July to mid-September, then rest in the deeper soil layers during later months. They begin to attack within 2 weeks after transplanting in July, completely checking plant growth. Attacked plants do not tiller and remain stunted; their leaves turn yellow. Yield losses in attacked fields amount to 30–50% or more. Normally 1–2 grubs/plant in the initial growth stage will cause economic damage. Incidence is maximum in August. During the hot summer months the grubs are found in earthen cocoons, 14–30 cm deep, in compact soil. The adults emerge in June–July and feed on grasses in the absence of rice, then lay eggs in the rice fields.

Incidence of root weevils^a in Haryana, India.

Grubs (no./plant) in		
1977-78	1978-79	1979-80
14.2	18.1	4.2
13.7	11.3	7.9
18.9	24.7	3.2
17.3	10.7	5.4
15.1	15.8	4.2
14.5	14.8	4.0
13.8	7.1	5.1
21.4	14.2	5.8
17.4	19.4	4.5
14.3	17.5	4.2

^aAv, 9 plants.

The yearly grub incidence in August in fields near the Kaul Rice Research Station averaged 13.7–21.4 grubs/plant in 1977–78; 7.1–24.7 grubs/plant in 1978–79; and 3.2–7.9 grubs/plant in 1979–80 (see table). The lower incidence in 1979–80 may be attributed to drought that season.

The Commonwealth Institute of Entomology identified the insects. ■

Present and future gall midge control strategies in South China

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A change in the cropping patterns of South China to two or three rice crops per year has resulted in outbreaks of gall midge *Orseolia oryzae*. In the past when rice was not available year round, the gall midge overwintered as larvae in the weed *Leersia hexandra* and in wild rice *Oryzae rufipogon*. But gall midge survival on these alternate hosts was low and the gall midge problem was less.

Control strategies based on 5 years of experiments have been implemented over the past 2 years to significantly decrease gall midge damage. These strategies combine cultural control, chemical control, and conservation of natural enemies. The development of host plant resistance and population forecasting with pheromones is being studied.

Cultural control involves timing the rice crops during periods of the year when the relative humidity is unfavorable to the gall midge. A high relative humidity (about 94%) is essential for larvae to hatch and penetrate into the rice tissue. Periodic draining of the fields during periods of favorable relative humidity is practiced. The continuous rice cycle is also broken by crop rotation or the establishment of rice-free fallow periods. The overwintering weed *L. hexandra* is removed by hand from the fields and field borders during the fallow periods.

Chemical control involves spraying or dusting during the peak of adult emergence, the rice tillering stage. The most effective insecticides are pyridofenthion, diazinon, dimethoate mixed with trichlorfon, and pyrimoxithion (N-23) [0-0-diethyl-0 (2-methoxy-4-methyl-pyrimidyl-6, phosphorothionate)]. A seedling dip with 0.1% trichlorfon is generally recommended to conserve natural enemies of the gall midge.

Root-zone application and soil incorporation of granules are popular among rice farmers in Kwangtung, Kiangsu, and other provinces. Root-zone application of pyrimoxithion or carbofuran, either in the seedbed or the field, was effective and is safe to parasites

and spiders. Stems of a tobacco cultivar containing 4% nicotine may be mixed with pyrimoxythion for root-zone application. Tobacco stems and leaves alone are effective if applied 5–6 days before the peak of emergence.

Five species of hymenopterous species have been found in Kwangtung: *Platygaster* sp. (polyembryonic), *Platygaster* sp. (monoembryonic), *Nenanastatus cinctiventris* Gir., *N. orientalis* Gir., and *Obtusiclava oryzae* Subba Rao. *Platygaster* (polyembryonic) usually predominates, but *Nenanastatus* increases to 70–80% during seedling and tillering stages of the late crop (both in seedbeds and in the field).

As much as 90% gall midge parasitization occurs in the late crop. Irrational insecticide application, however, kills

natural enemies and may encourage gall midge resurgence. Gall midge parasitization in the overwintering generation in wild rice reached 65% in 1976 investigations in San-Huan brigade, Hua County, Kwangtung. Parasitization reached 32–33% in the first and second generations of the early crop, but dropped to 2–5% in late-crop seedbeds (compared with 44% in untreated fields) because of frequent applications (4- to 5-day intervals) of methyl parathion-BHC and dimethoate. The order of toxicity to *Platygaster* sp. as contact poisons was pyrimoxythion > trichlorfon > dimethoate > 2, 5-dimethylphenyl-N-methylcarbamate > chlordimeform.

The growing of gall midge-resistant varieties such as Bao Tou San 2 and Qui Yang Nai 121 is being investigated.

Resistant varieties have been tested and biotype variations are being determined in cooperation with the International Rice Testing Program. Research indicates that resistance is antibiotic — under the same infestation conditions larvae were still in the first instar 7 days after hatching in Bao Tou San 2, but all larvae had molted into the second instar in a susceptible variety.

Preliminary experiments on the use of pheromone traps for monitoring and as a control measure are promising. An extract by dichloromethane of the virgin female attracts males at night. Large numbers of males and females have been caught in light trap-pheromone extract combinations. The sex pheromone is being purified and identified; it seems to be an ester. ■

Root-zone application of systemic insecticides for insect control in China

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Results of 5 years' experiments in South China indicated that root-zone application of systemic insecticides effectively controlled almost all potential insect pests of rice: the yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas*, the striped stem borer *Chilo suppressalis*, the pink borer *Sesamia inferens*, the rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*, the rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae*, the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*, the green leafhopper *Nephotettix* spp., the rice thrips *Baliothrips biformis*, and the rice root weevil *Echinocnemus squameus*.

In extensive trials of 14 compounds, 1 root-zone application of carbofuran granules at 1.5 kg a.i./ha effectively controlled gall midge, yellow stem borer, pink borer, rice thrips, green leafhopper, and brown planthopper. Root-zone carbofuran remained effective against borers 40–60 days; they remained effective against the brown planthopper 30 days after application. One application of carbofuran granules by

The effectiveness of thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate (Evisect) for the control of the yellow stem borer and rice thrips. Dosage: 1.5 kg a.i./ha. Root-zone application is better than broadcast.

soil incorporation in rice seedbeds gave good field control of 1 gall midge generation and 2 other pests. The rice seedlings carried the insecticide into the paddy after transplanting with no adverse effects on the egg-larval parasite *Platygaster* spp. This method of carbofuran application is popular among rice farmers in Kwangtung, Kiangsu, and other provinces.

Although carbofuran is a broad-spectrum insecticide, its effectiveness against the leaf folder is low. In fields with heavy leaf folder infestation, application of carbofuran mixed with padan, or dimehypo, or chlordimeform is recommended.

Nereistoxin made from a marine annelid has served as a base for a group of useful insecticides. When applied in the root-

zone, the nereistoxin derivatives padan, dimehypo, and thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate (“Evisect,” see photo) (San 1551) have recently been found to be good systemic insecticides for control of stem borers, leaf folder, and thrips. These compounds, selective contact and stomach insecticides, act as synaptic blocking agents. Their mode of action differs completely from those of organophosphorus and carbamate compounds. The long residual action of soil-applied padan — as long as 50 days after treatment — was outstanding for yellow borer control.

Most farmers in China still rely mainly on cultural practices and insecticides for pest control because biological control agents — including *Trichogramma*, *Bacillus thuringiensis*, spiders, and